

A New Triterpene from *Limnophila rugosa* (Roth.) Merrill

K S MUKHERJEE*, G BRAHMACHARI, T K MANNA and S LAHA

Department of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati University, Santiniketan-731 235

Manuscript received 9 February 1994, accepted 1 March 1994

In continuation of our previous works on *Limnophila rugosa*¹, we now report herein the isolation and characterisation of a new triterpene from the benzene extract of this plant. The concentrated benzene extract of air-dried defatted whole plants (aerial parts and roots) of *L. rugosa* was chromatographed over silica gel (60–120 mesh) using solvents with increasing polarity. The chloroform eluate afforded a compound, C₃₀H₄₆O₄ (*M*⁺, *m/z* 470) crystallised from acetone as white needles, m.p. 135–36°; gave pinkish colouration in Liebermann-Burchard test for triterpene and responded to Zimmermann test; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 400 (OH), 1 720 (six-membered C=O) and 1 695 cm⁻¹ (C=O) (90 MHz CDCl₃) (3H, s), 0.85 (6H, s), 0.90 (6H, s), 1.12 (6H, s) for seven tertiary C-CH₃ 5.40 (1H, m vinylic unsaturation) and 3.55 (1H, t), CH(OH). The compound readily formed a methyl ester, C₃₁H₄₈O₄ (*M*⁺, *m/z* 484) (2), m.p. 140°, on treatment with diazomethane in ether, and on acetylation with acetic anhydride in pyridine, formed an amorphous monoacetyl derivative, C₃₂H₄₈O₅ (*M*⁺, *m/z* 512) (3). The mass spectrum of the parent triterpene is typical of Δ^{12} -oleanene skeleton², and exhibited peaks at *m/z* 470 (*M*⁺), 425, 248, 203, 221, 133, suggesting the presence of carboxylic group in D/E ring portion and keto and hydroxyl functions in A/B ring portion.

On reduction with LiAlH₄, the parent triterpene formed a triol, C₃₀H₅₀O₃ (4), m.p. 212°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 500 (OH) and 1 680 cm⁻¹ (C=C), which has been found to be identical with 1,3,28-trihydroxyolean-12-ene³, by comparison of physical and spectral data. This settles the location of hydroxyl and keto functions either in the positions C₁ and C₃ and carboxylic group in C₁₇-position in the parent compound. The positive response to Zimmermann test by the triterpene conclusively locates the keto

at C₃, consequently the hydroxyl must be at C₁-position. Finally, the appearance of the carbinol-methylene proton (-CHOH) at δ 3.55 (1H, t) which shifted to δ 4.50 in the acetate derivative (3) assigns the equatorial and β -orientation of the OH group at C₁. Thus, the new triterpene derivative is β -Hydroxy-3-keto-olean-12-en-28-oic acid (1).

1, R = O,	R ₁ = OH,	R ₂ = COOH
2; R = O,	R ₁ = OH,	R ₂ = COOCH ₃
3; R = O,	R ₁ = OAc,	R ₂ = COOH
4; R = H(OH),	R ₁ = OH,	R ₂ = CH ₂ OH

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to R.S.I.C., I.I.T., Madras and C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for spectral measurements, and are grateful to C.S.I.R. and U.G.C., New Delhi, for awarding Junior Research Fellowships to two of them (T.K.M. and G.B. respectively).

References

- 1 K. S. MUKHERJEE, C. K. CHAKRABORTY and T. P. CHATTERJEE, *Phytochemistry*, 1989, **28**, 1778; K. S. MUKHERJEE, C. K. CHAKRABORTY, D. BHATTACHARYA and T. P. CHATTERJEE, *Fitoterapia*, 1990, **66**, 366; K. S. MUKHERJEE, C. K. CHAKRABORTY, T. P. CHATTERJEE and D. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **67**, 89; K. S. MUKHERJEE, S. LAHA, T. K. MANNA and C. K. CHAKRABORTY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **69**, 411; K. S. MUKHERJEE, S. LAHA, T. K. MANNA and S. C. ROY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1995, **72**, 63
- 2 H. BUDZIKIEWICZ, J. M. WILSON and C. DJERASSI, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 3688.
- 3 A. ULUBELFEN and K. AYANOGLU, *Phytochemistry*, 1976, **15**, 309

